

EFFECTS OF SHORT CARBON FIBERS APPLICATION IN MAGNESIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Carbon fibers because of their excellent mechanical properties and low density are well known reinforcing material in composites. Commercial carbon fibers are applied in form of multifilament yarns, fabrics or preforms convenient mainly for polymer matrices. In case of above described reinforcement but for light metals matrices composites technologies however, with short time metal infiltration process required, formation of non-wetted parallel fibers and compacted fibers areas are observed.

In the present paper 3D granules of single fibers were applied for the infiltration by magnesium and their alloys, and the results of structural investigation are presented.

2 Fibers Preparation

2.1 Manufacturing of 3D Granules

In the experiment carbon fibers T300B (Toray) and NF3 (Sigrafil) with different diameter, in form of multifilament yarn were mechanically cut and mechanically mixed in the process ensuring formation of 3D granules with diameter of 3-5 mm. Obtained carbon component was consisted of uniformly distributed single short fibers long 100-1000 μ m without any preferable orientation (Fig. 1 and 2).

2.2 Fibers Surface Modification

In our own experiments the possibility of carbon fibers surface modification with nanolayers was examined. Granules were coated with TiC, HfC, TiN and SiO₂ nanolayers by chemical vapor deposition (CVD), reactive chemical deposition (RCVD) and sol-gel methods [1,2]. Good results were obtained for RCVD method but the

from required nanocoating quality point of view the best process seems to be the sol-gel (Fig.3).

3 Magnesium Matrix Composite with Short Carbon Fibers

3.1 Composite Microstructure

Wettability of uncoated and coated fibers was preliminary tested in argon atmosphere and obtained results showed the utility of only TiN and SiO₂ nanolayers in systems with magnesium. Composites were obtained by pressure infiltration with different pressure conditions or by pressureless cast technology. Independently on applied technological process the case of non-wetted parallel fibers and compacted fibers was observed only accidentally (Fig. 4 and 5).

3.2 Interface Microstructure

Investigation of interface microstructure were carried out by scanning electron microscopy combined with energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM+EDS) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). They showed a reactive type of bonding between components, demonstrated by the presence of the oxides and carbides containing zone at the interface. Its composition depended on magnesium alloy composition and fibers surface feature with or without additional nanolayer. The influence of oxygen absorbed by carbon fibers on interface microstructure formation was observed independently on fibers surface modification.

4 Summary

Presented experiment showed the utility of short C_f in form of 3D dispersed fibers granules in manufacturing of magnesium matrix composites. That form of fibers with unmodified or modified surface ensured proper conditions for liquid metal

infiltration and evident reduction of the compacted and non-wetted fiber area formation.

Fig.1. Microstructure of 3D granule of short Toraya C_f , SEM.

Fig.2. Microstructure of 3D granule of short Sigrafil C_f , SEM.

Fig.3. Surface of single C_f coated with nanolayer of SiO_2 , SEM.

Fig.4. Microstructure of magnesium matrix composites reinforced with C_f in form of 3D granule of short fibers, cross-section, SEM.

Fig.5. Microstructure of magnesium matrix composites reinforced with C_f in form of 3D granule of short fibers, fracture, SEM.

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References

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